

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PREPARATION OF 2,6-DIMETHYL-4-VINYLPHENOL (2,6.DM4VF) WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF A MODIFIED NiO-Fe₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ CATALYST

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ABSTRACT

During the study, a method for obtaining 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol from 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol in the presence of a nickel-iron and chromium-containing oxide catalyst was studied. As a result, the effect of temperature on the dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol was studied at other values of the input parameters, that is, at a given HS of the feedstock mixture of 1.5 st-1 and at a ratio of 1 : 12 : 1 of ethyl xylene to water and benzene, which are the feedstock components. From the analysis of these results, it is clear that the effect of temperature on the dehydrogenation reaction is significant. and as a result of its application, good opportunities have opened up for meeting the demand for valuable monomers, including 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol.

Keywords: Catalyst, 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol, 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol, dehydrogenation.

INTRODUCTION

Among low-molecular-weight alkenylphenols, representatives of which the ethyl bond is conjugated with the benzene nucleus, including vinylphenol, vinylcresol, and vinylxylenes, occupy a special place. The presence of reactive functional groups in the structure of vinylphenols opens up wide possibilities for obtaining a wide variety of their derivatives and, in particular, for increasing the variety of monomers for polymer chemistry [1].

A large number of technical products with interesting properties, such as layered plastic masses, coatings, resins, photosensitive materials, adhesives, molding masses, building reagents, vitamins, etc., are produced based on vinylphenols. The polymers obtained on their basis have high adhesion, are selected for their heat resistance and chemical resistance.

Studies conducted mainly on the synthesis of p-vinylphenol, which has high reactivity, and the production of polymers based on it have not been applied to other vinyl xylenes. A detailed study of the dehydrogenation reaction of ethyl xylenes with the participation of a selected catalyst can be a major step towards investigating the influence of the nature of the catalyst, reaction conditions, and other factors on the course of the process, the composition and characteristics of the reaction products, determining its regularities, and establishing the scientific foundations of the process. [2-3]

Conducting the research process

The dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol to obtain 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol with the participation of a modified NiO-Fe₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ catalyst was studied in detail.

When ethylxylenes are converted under the conditions of a dehydrogenation reaction to obtain vinylcresols, a number of undesirable side reactions occur in addition to the dehydrogenation reaction, among which the dealkylation reaction predominates (Table 1). The sum of the concentrations of phenol, cresol, and xylenol obtained by the dealkylation reaction during the catalytic conversion of ethyl xylenol is more than 4 times higher at temperatures of 500–520°C, 1.7 times higher at temperatures of 540°C, and more than 1.3 times higher at temperatures of 560°C than the sum of the concentrations of these substances obtained during the conversion of ethyl cresol. The concentrations of gaseous substances and condensation products during the dehydrogenation reaction of ethyl xylenols with the participation of the studied catalyst were also 1.1÷1.9 times higher. As a result, the dehydrogenation fraction of ethyl xylene, which is considered the target reaction, is significantly reduced in the catalytic system. This also has a negative effect on the selectivity of the reaction to the target product and the yield of the main product [4-6].

Studies aimed at partially moderating the dehydrogenation reaction conditions have been successful. Lowering the partial pressure of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol (increasing the molar ratios of water and benzene) and reducing its contact time with the catalyst have significantly reduced the share of side reactions in catalytic conversions.

Table 1.

Effect of temperature on the dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol with the participation of a modified NiO-Fe₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ catalyst.

Reaction conditions: HS - 1.0 st-1, 2,6DM4EF in water and benzene
MN = 1 : 10 : 0.8.

Temperature, 0C	500	520	540	560
Product and indicator name				
Received by mass %, including				
Phenol	-	0.4	0.8	1.5
Cresols	0.5	0.8	1.4	2.2
Xylenols	1.2	1.5	2.6	2.5
2,6DM4EF	60.0	51.5	43.0	36.0
2,6DM4VF	35.2	41.7	46.1	49.4
Dimer	0.5	0.8	1.2	1.0
Trimmer	-	0.3	0.6	1.4
Unidentified substances	1.2	1.4	1.8	2.2
Gas + loss	1.4	1.6	2.5	3.8

Taking this into account, the effect of temperature on the dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol was studied at other values of the input parameters, i.e., when the HS of the given feedstock mixture was 1.5 st-1 and the ratio of ethyl xylene to water and benzene, which are the feedstock components, was 1 : 12 : 1. The obtained results are reflected in the table (Table 2). It is clear from the analysis of these results that the effect of temperature on the dehydrogenation reaction is significant.

As with ethylcresols, increasing temperature increases the conversion of ethylxylene. This isomer of ethylxylene, which undergoes a remarkable degree of conversion, forms a series of products. When examining table (2), it becomes clear that the catalysts contain phenol, cresol, xylenes, 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol, its dimer and trimer, and unidentified substances as gaseous products.

Table 2

Effect of temperature on the dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol with the participation of a modified NiO-Fe₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ catalyst.

Reaction conditions: HS-1.0 st-1, 2,6DM4EF in water and benzene
MN-i=1 : 12 : 1.

Temperature, 0C	500	520	540	560
Product and indicator name				
Received by mass %, including				
Phenol	-	-	0.6	1.2
Cresols	0.2	0.6	1.2	2.2
Xylenols	0.8	1.2	1.8	2.0
2,6DM4EF	62.2	53.0	45.2	38.9
2,6DM4VF	34.6	41.8	46.1	48.6
Dimer	-	0.6	1.0	1.0
Trimmer	-	-	0.5	1.1
Unidentified substances	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.8
Gas + loss	1.0	1.4	2.0	3.2

The complexity of the composition of the reaction products indicates that a series of parallel and sequential transformations occur during the process. The main

transformation among them is the dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol, which occurs according to the following scheme.

The main reaction product, 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol, is the most abundant of the reaction products. This is also reflected in the yield of the target product. Increasing the temperature initially has little effect on the selectivity of the reaction to the target product. Thus, increasing the temperature from 500 0C

to 520 0C reduces the selectivity from 92.8% to 90.3%, which is also a small change. The main side conversion in the dehydrogenation process of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol with the participation of the studied catalyst is its dealkylation reaction. An increase in temperature accelerates the onset of this side conversion.

Analysis of the composition of the catalysts has shown that the dealkylation process most likely occurs according to a stepwise scheme, i.e. first deethylation, and then demethylation occur sequentially [4-6].

It is more likely that the dealkylation process occurs according to the scheme shown above, but it is also

While at lower temperatures (500 – 520 0C) a greater production of xylenols is observed, at a temperature of 540 0C a sufficient amount of cresols and phenol is formed, i.e. dealkylation deepens.

At a temperature of 560 0C, cresols predominate among the dealkylation products.

Thus, in the cresols formed in the temperature range of 500 - 560 0C, the main isomer is 2-methylphenol, and in the mixture of xylenes - 2,6-dimethylphenol. This fact clearly proves our statements. In addition, the cresols and xylenes obtained during the process are subject to isomerization, albeit partially. As a result, under the most severe reaction conditions, up to 6.0% of o-cresol and up to 6.8% of 2,6-xylene undergo intramolecular transformations, with isomerization prevailing among them. As can be seen from Table 5, in the cresol mixture obtained at a temperature of 560 0C, 5.0% by mass of m-isomer and 1.0% by mass of p-cresol are obtained. In the xylene mixture obtained under these conditions, the concentration of 2,5-isomer is 4.9%, and the concentration of 2,4-xylene is 1.9% by mass. It should also be noted that, compared to ethylxylenols, the exposure of the cresols and xylenols obtained in the dehydrogenation process to the isomerization reaction is slightly lower (1.5 - 2.2%).

possible that the first stage of dealkylation begins with demethylation and occurs at the ethyl group in position 4.

In general, the intramolecular transformation reactions of alkylphenols obtained in the dehydrogenation processes of ethyl xylenes are most likely thermocatalytic in nature [7]. The analysis of the catalytic properties of the modified complex oxide catalyst, determined as a result of numerous studies, gives us reason to base ourselves on this idea.

Increasing the temperature of the dehydrogenation process of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol leads to a significant increase in the production of gaseous products and losses, which are considered other by-products. Methane and ethane are the predominant gaseous products. The loss substances include carbon-like compounds that accumulate on the catalyst surface.

Analysis of the obtained results (Tables 1 and 2) shows that raising the temperature above 520 0C is not favorable for the process of obtaining 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol, because>The complex composition of catalysts obtained at temperatures above 520 0C creates a number of difficulties in their subsequent processing, and negatively affects the performance and purity of the target product.

Table 3.

Isomeric composition of cresols and xylenols formed in the dehydrogenation reaction of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol with the participation of a modified NiO-Fe2O3-Cr2O3 catalyst.

Reaction conditions			Isomer composition of cresol in mass %			Isomer composition of xylene by mass %		
T 0C	HS, st-1	2.6DM4EF's MN with water and benzene	oh-	m-	p-	2.6-	2.5-	2.4-
500	1.5	1:12:1	100	-	-	100	-	-
520	1.5	1:12:1	98.0	2.0	-	99.2	0.8	-
540	1.5	1:12:1	95.7	4.8	0.5	97.0	2.8	0.4
560	1.5	1:12:1	94.0	5.0	1.0	93.2	4.9	1.9
520	0.5	1:12:1	95.8	2.2	2.0	96.0	3.2	0.8

For this reason, studies were continued by changing the values of other input parameters affecting the

dehydrogenation process at a temperature of 520 0C, where higher and more favorable results were obtained.

In general, although the fact that there is an inverse relationship between the conversion of ethyl xylene and the selectivity of the reaction to the target product is confirmed for this process, in some cases this relationship is not sharp. In general, the yield of 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol, calculated from the starting 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol, decreases with increasing rate and is 28.2% at $HS = 3.0$ st-1. In the next stage of the research, the effect of the molar ratio (MN) of ethyl xylene, water, and benzene, which are the raw components, on the dehydrogenation process of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol with the participation of the catalyst we selected, was studied.

In general, as a result of a detailed study of the effect of these input parameters on the dehydrogenation reaction, it was determined that the most favorable value of the molar ratio of ethyl xylene to water and benzene in the feedstock is 1:12:1.

As a result, the dehydrogenation process of 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol with the participation of a modified Ni-Fe-Cr (MNDX) oxide complex catalytic system was studied in detail, the main and side transformations occurring during this process were determined, the effect of various input parameters on the dehydrogenation process was studied, and favorable reaction conditions for the high yield and production of 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol with S were revealed ($T = 520$ °C, $HS = 1.5$ st-1, MN of 2.6.DM4EF in water and benzene - 1 : 12 : 1). This method, proposed for the preparation of 2,6-dimethyl-4-vinylphenol, is economically and ecologically advantageous and allows the synthesis of a new and structurally interesting monomer for polymer chemistry, opening up great opportunities for its use in this direction for the first time.

RESULT

The dehydrogenation reaction of ethyl xylenes, including 2,6-dimethyl-4-ethylphenol, was studied in detail for the first time with the participation of a modified

NiO-Fe₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ (MNDX) oxide catalyst. The effect of input parameters on the chemistry and performance of the process was studied and its realization in a series-parallel scheme was revealed. Favorable conditions for both reactions were determined ($T=520$ °C, $\nu=1.5$ st-1 (molar ratio of ethyl xylenol to water and benzene 1:12:1) and high yield (42.4-44.1%) and selectivity (88.8-90.3%) of vinyl xylenols were obtained. The proposed method enables the synthesis of new and interesting structural monomers and opens up great possibilities for their use.

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